

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR STRATEGIC DECISION- MAKING IN INFRASTRUCTURE ENGINEERING PROJECT MANAGEMENT

¹Olusola Temitope Ayo-Soyemi, ²Daniel Oluwaseun Oyalakun,

¹Engineering Project Manager |MSc Information Management, ² Ph.D. Candidate Business Administration

¹Department of Computer and Information Sciences,

¹University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, United Kingdom

Abstract : This study examined the application of artificial intelligence for strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management. The study's main objective was to determine the effect of cloud computing, machine learning algorithms, and data collection and processing on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management. This study adopted a survey research design. The study was carried out among the staff of Julius Berger Nigeria Plc. in Lagos State, Nigeria. Lagos State was chosen because the state has the highest number of infrastructure engineering companies and is regarded as the economic center in the country. The staff of this company were randomly chosen, sixty-six (66) staff were found to be the sample size contacted in filling out the questionnaire. In testing the hypotheses the study found out that, the use of cloud computing has contributed positively ($R^2 = 0.851$ and $P=.000$) to the strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management, the use of machine learning algorithms has contributed positively ($R^2 = 0.643$ and $P=.000$) to the strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management, and the use of AI for data collection and processing has contributed positively ($R^2 = 0.407$ and $P=.000$) to the strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management. The study recommends that infrastructure engineers should always engage in the usage of artificial intelligence when making strategic decisions on project management.

IndexTerms - Artificial Intelligence, Strategic Decision-making, Infrastructure Engineering, Project Management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence is essential in many areas and aspects in the majority of nations worldwide. The term artificial intelligence (AI) is widely used. Our civilizations make extensive use of AI, which has profound effects on the political, social, and economic spheres (Al Marzooqi, El Khatib, Mahmood, & AlAmeemi, 2023). These days, artificial intelligence is being used more and more in a variety of industries to help improve our employment. Due to the high cost of AI tools and techniques, AI has been used in the most innovative fields, supply chain and logistics, chatbots, streamlined manufacturing, machine learning, which is highly consumed in AI-powered project management, complex and sustainable projects, and many other areas (Yasir et al., 2022). Furthermore, evaluating the impact of project management including AI tools is important. Assessing labor and cost savings, creating income, boosting productivity, lowering biases and errors, and many other processes can help achieve this (Aljumah et al., 2022a; Amiri et al., 2020).

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) is causing a radical change in the field of project management (Zhou et al., 2024). AI's analytical skills and learning capabilities can be extremely helpful in areas that are frequently beset by large data processing, unanticipated events, human constraints, and in infrastructural engineering. Making decisions in complicated infrastructural engineering projects can be difficult. Finding the best solutions is challenging for project managers because they are constantly inundated with data, budgets, schedules, and resource allocation. Conventional approaches frequently depend on experience and intuition, which can be arbitrary and error-prone. Another challenge is risk management. Unexpected things might happen in complex projects, so it's critical to recognize possible risks early and set priorities for them. But doing so frequently necessitates sorting through mountains of data, which may be a laborious and resource-intensive process (Weng et al., 2024). According to Akour et al. (2022), automation based on artificial intelligence plays a major role in the adoption of smart cities and buildings, which is one of the primary concerns in construction. According to Al-Dmour et al. (2023), these devices can save time, effort, and money, and provide sustainability by executing tasks automatically. The project manager can control and monitor the project with the use of AI technologies and techniques.

Predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms are two examples of AI technologies that help optimize resource allocation, cut waste, and simplify project management procedures, all of which can lead to significant cost savings. Construction companies that operate in a highly competitive market with small profit margins will find this especially tempting. Another important consideration is improving safety on building sites. Real-time site condition monitoring, hazard prediction, and worker alerting are all made possible by AI-powered systems (Darko et al., 2020; Sacks et al., 2020; Abioye et al., 2021). AI, for example, can examine data from wearable technology to identify indicators of employee stress or weariness, preventing mishaps. In addition to safeguarding employees, this proactive approach reduces project delays and accident-related financial costs. The deployment of AI is further fueled by the growing complexity of construction projects. Intricate designs and complex engineering specifications are common in modern construction (Rane, Desai & Rane, 2024). The study will address the gap in knowledge on the application of artificial intelligence for strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The broad objective of this research is to ascertain the application of artificial intelligence for strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management. The specific objectives are to:

- i. determine the effect of cloud computing on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.
- ii. examine the effect of machine learning algorithms on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.
- iii. determine the effect of data collection and processing on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 CONCEPT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

According to Mahmood, Al Marzooqi, El Khatib, and AlAmeemi (2023), artificial intelligence refers to computers designed to mimic human intellect in order to perform and learn like a human brain would. Aljumah et al. (2021) claim that AI is automating these activities by utilizing machine learning to create models that capture human behavior. Making judgments more quickly based on vast amounts of data is an example of applying AI technologies (Al-Marouf et al., 2022). Additionally, the infrastructure of an organization can use the large data from smart building systems to implement intelligent controls for buildings, such as improving grid stability, lowering energy consumption, and improving occupant comfort. Additionally, the intelligent analysis, interpretation, and distribution of efficient and effective actions in real-time are enhanced by the integration of AI technology with smart building systems (Al-Marouf et al., 2022b; Khatib, 2022).

2.2 FACTORS AFFECTING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN INFRASTRUCTURE ENGINEERING PROJECT MANAGEMENT

2.2.1 CLOUD COMPUTING

With its scale and flexibility, cloud computing is a major facilitator of AI integration in construction management. Cloud-based infrastructure enables the smooth scaling of computing resources according to project requirements, even while construction projects vary in size and complexity (Adewusi et al., 2024). One of the most important benefits of cloud computing for AI integration is real-time data processing. Timely decision-making is essential for construction projects, and cloud-based solutions make it easier to analyze incoming data streams quickly. Cloud computing guarantees that AI algorithms can digest information quickly, whether it's sensor data from the building site or real-time collaboration updates. Construction managers can make well-informed decisions more quickly thanks to real-time data processing, which improves AI systems' reactivity (Adelekan et al., 2024).

2.2.2 MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

The intelligence underlying AI applications in construction management is derived from machine learning techniques (Okoli et al., 2024). To identify trends, correlations, and possible risk indicators, these algorithms can be trained on previous project data. Training entails exposing the algorithms to a wide range of data, such as details on previous project results, difficulties encountered, and effective tactics used. Machine learning models gain the ability to classify data, make predictions, and improve decision-making through this training process. AI systems may recognize best practices, foresee possible problems, and aid in better project planning for construction management when models are trained using previous project data (Eboigbe et al., 2023).

2.2.3 DATA COLLECTION AND PROCESSING

The gathering of varied and up-to-date data is the cornerstone of integrating AI into construction management. In this procedure, sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) devices are essential (Odonkor et al., 2024). These devices, which are integrated into machinery, construction equipment, and the actual construction site, produce an ongoing flow of data about environmental conditions, equipment performance, and project activities. Sensors can keep an eye on variables like temperature, humidity, vibration, and location, giving important information about the project's status and possible problems. These sensors may be seamlessly connected thanks to IoT devices, which makes it easier to create a networked environment that provides data to AI systems for analysis and decision-making. According to Kaggwa et al. (2024), effective data storage and accessibility are essential elements of a successful AI integration.

2.3 CHALLENGES AND CONSIDERATIONS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN INFRASTRUCTURAL ENGINEERING

While there are many potential advantages of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into construction management, there are also several issues and concerns that must be carefully considered. For AI technologies to be successfully implemented and remain viable over the long term in the construction industry, several issues must be resolved.

2.3.1 PRIVACY AND DATA SECURITY ISSUES

Numerous sensitive data points are involved in construction projects, including personnel information, financial data, and project plans. It is crucial to guarantee the privacy and security of this data (Reis et al., 2024). Adopting AI frequently entails gathering and analyzing large datasets, and project stakeholders run the danger of sensitive information being revealed (Farayola et al., 2023). For processing and storing data, AI systems mostly rely on cloud-based services and network connectivity. Construction projects are more vulnerable to cybersecurity risks including data breaches and illegal access as a result of this interconnection. Strong cybersecurity measures are necessary to safeguard construction data and AI-generated insights from malevolent actors (Abrahams et al., 2024).

2.3.2 ACCEPTANCE AND TRAINING OF THE WORKFORCE

For AI to be successfully incorporated into construction management, a workforce with the necessary skills to comprehend and utilize these technologies is needed. The construction sector may, however, have serious talent shortages, with current employees lacking the know-how to use AI tools and platforms efficiently. Any industry experiencing technological development frequently faces resistance to change (Atadoga et al., 2024).

2.3.3 INITIAL EXPENSES OF IMPLEMENTATION

A substantial initial financial outlay is required to integrate AI into construction management. Budgets for projects may be strained by the cost of acquiring the required technology, software, and knowledge, particularly for smaller construction companies. Widespread adoption of AI technology may be delayed by some stakeholders perceived high initial costs (Valentina et al., 2021).

2.3.4 INTEGRATION WITH CURRENT FRAMEWORKS

Numerous construction companies currently have procedures and systems in place. Compatibility problems may arise when integrating AI with current systems, necessitating modifications or enhancements to guarantee smooth integration. Data silos brought on by incompatibility can lessen the usefulness of insights powered by AI. Legacy equipment and infrastructure are frequently used in construction projects, and they might not be easily compatible with contemporary AI technologies. There are financial and logistical obstacles to upgrading or modifying current infrastructure to facilitate AI integration. Careful planning and evaluation of AI systems' compatibility with the current technological environment are necessary for successful integration (Oguejiofor et al., 2023).

2.4 FUTURE TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENTS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN INFRASTRUCTURE ENGINEERING

The future of artificial intelligence (AI) in construction management is full of exciting possibilities, according to Obiuto et al. (2024). These opportunities are fueled by ongoing improvements in AI technologies, growing industry adoption, and possible partnerships with other cutting-edge technologies. The expected advances and trends in AI for construction management are examined in this section.

2.4.1 DEVELOPMENTS IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR CONSTRUCTION MANAGEMENT

More advanced predictive analytics capabilities are anticipated from future AI technologies in construction management (Farayola et al., 2023). Larger datasets may be analyzed by sophisticated machine learning algorithms, which will provide more precise forecasts for project budgets, schedules, and possible hazards. This will enable construction teams to optimize project tactics and make even better selections. AI developments will make it possible to monitor and manage building projects in real-time. Advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) features may be incorporated into future AI advancements to improve communication between AI systems and construction teams. More natural and efficient communication will be made possible by AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants with enhanced language comprehension, which will streamline information sharing and teamwork among project stakeholders (Farayola et al., 2023).

2.4.2 INDUSTRY-WIDE ADOPTION AND STANDARDIZATION

There will probably be more education and training programs in the construction sector as people become more aware of the advantages of AI in management. Professionals in the construction industry will aim to comprehend and gain the abilities required to use AI tools efficiently. The workforce will become more knowledgeable and tech-savvy as a result of industry-wide education initiatives. Standardized data formats and procedures will be established as a result of the broad use of AI in the construction industry. Ensuring interoperability across various AI applications and facilitating smooth integration with current systems depends on this standardization.

2.4.3 POTENTIAL COLLABORATION WITH ADDITIONAL CUTTING-EDGE TECHNOLOGIES (SUCH AS DRONES AND ROBOTICS)

There is a lot of promise for monitoring building sites when AI and drone technologies work together. AI algorithms can evaluate data collected by drones with sophisticated sensors and cameras in real-time (Thakur et al., 2021). This cooperative method improves site monitoring accuracy, offers comprehensive visual insights, and helps construction project managers make better decisions. On-site building processes are about to undergo a revolution because to the combination of robotics and artificial intelligence. Robotic systems can have their movements guided and optimized by AI algorithms, increasing their accuracy and efficiency. On construction sites, collaborative robots, or cobots, may operate alongside humans to complete repetitive jobs and enhance safety and productivity (Adegbite et al., 2023).

2.5 THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.5.1 UNIFIED THEORY OF ACCEPTANCE AND USE OF TECHNOLOGY (UTAUT)

Based on TAM, Venkatesh et al. (2000) presented the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), which highlights four key factors that drive technology acceptance: social influence, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and facilitating conditions. Performance expectancy, as used in the construction industry, is the conviction that applying AI would result in better performance, such as improved quality control or project efficiency. Similar to perceived ease of use in TAM, effort

expectations highlight how crucial it is to keep AI solutions as simple as possible. Peer pressure and the views of powerful industry players are captured by social influence, which shows how industry leaders' recommendations can have a big impact on acceptance. For AI technologies to be successfully implemented in the construction industry, enabling conditions include the availability of resources and support, such as technical assistance and training programs.

2.5.2 DIFFUSION OF INNOVATIONS (DOI) THEORY

Everett Rogers (1962) introduced the Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) theory which provides a thorough framework for comprehending how new concepts and technology proliferate within a community or sector. According to DOI, the adoption of AI in the construction industry can be studied through five characteristics: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. The idea that AI technologies are better than current approaches is known as relative advantage. For example, by anticipating equipment breakdowns, AI-driven predictive maintenance can provide large cost savings, making it an obvious advantage. Compatibility evaluates how well AI integrates with construction companies' current procedures and operations. The perceived difficulty of comprehending and utilizing AI systems is addressed by complexity. Trialability is the degree to which AI can be tested in a restricted setting before being widely used. Last but not least, observability refers to the benefits of AI being visible, for example, through case studies or pilot projects showing effective AI applications in the construction industry.

2.5.3 INNOVATION RESISTANCE THEORY (IRT)

Ram and Sheth's 1989 introduction of the Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) sheds light on the opposition to innovative technology. IRT highlights that psychological (emotional and cognitive) and functional (practical) barriers might be the source of resistance. Functional hurdles in the construction sector could include worries about AI systems' dependability, the expense of installation, or possible disruptions to current operations. Psychological obstacles may include resistance to altering long-standing procedures, mistrust of AI decision-making, or fear of losing one's job. It is essential to comprehend these obstacles in order to create solutions that will lessen opposition, such as open communication, proving the dependability of AI, and emphasizing how AI complements human talents rather than replace them.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

This study adopted a survey research design. The study was carried out among the staff of Julius Berger Nigeria Plc. in Lagos State, Nigeria. Lagos State was chosen because the state has the highest number of infrastructure engineering companies and is regarded as the economic center in the country.

3.2 POPULATION AND SAMPLE

The population of the study is the staff of the company who are qualified to fill the questionnaire which consists of ninety (90) staff and was randomly chosen, sixty-six (66) staff were found to be the sample size that matches the population of the study.

3.3 DATA AND SOURCES OF DATA

The engineers were contacted to fill out the questionnaire which serves as primary data to achieve the objectives of the study, and the questionnaire was the research instrument used. The responses of the respondents in the questionnaires were ranked on a 5-point scale of Strongly Agree; Agree; Undecided; Disagree; and Strongly Disagree.

3.4 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

Inferential statistics with the use of regression analysis were employed as a statistical tool to analyze the data obtained from the respondents with the aid of SPSS vs23.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 TEST OF HYPOTHESES

4.1.1 HYPOTHESIS ONE (HO1)

Data collection and processing do not have a significant effect on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

Table 4.1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.923 ^a	.851	.849	1.25869

a. Predictors: (Constant), Cloud computing

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 4.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	589.498	1	589.498	372.088	.000 ^b
	Residual	102.979	65	1.584		
	Total	692.478	66			

a. Dependent Variable: Strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management

b. Predictors: (Constant), Cloud computing

Source: Field Survey (2024)

The result above shows the model summary table that revealed the extent to which the variance in artificial intelligence can be explained by cloud computing is 85.1% i.e. (R square = 0.851). The ANOVA table shows the Fcal 372.088. The significance level is .000 which implies statistical confidence of 95%. Considering this, the decision would be to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) and accept the alternate hypothesis (Ho). This implies that data collection and processing have a significant effect on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

This result aligns with the findings of Adewusi et al., (2024) and Adelekan et al., (2024). In their studies on the use of cloud computing in construction industries to achieve the objectives of project management, in which the use of cloud computing has a significant effect on project management in construction companies. Cloud computing thus tends to improve strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

4.1.2 HYPOTHESIS TWO (HO2)

Machine learning algorithms do not have a significant effect on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

Table 4.3 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.802 ^a	.643	.638	1.95003

a. Predictors: (Constant), Machine learning algorithms

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 4.4 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	445.308	1	445.308	117.106	.000 ^b
	Residual	247.169	65	3.803		
	Total	692.478	66			

a. Dependent Variable: Strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management

b. Predictors: (Constant), Machine learning algorithms

Source: Field Survey (2024)

The result above shows the model summary table that revealed the extent to which the variance in artificial intelligence can be explained by machine learning algorithms is 64.3% i.e. (R square = 0.643). The ANOVA table shows the Fcal 117.106. The significance level is .000 which implies a statistical confidence of 95%. Considering this, the decision would be to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) and accept the alternate hypothesis (Ho). This implies that machine learning algorithms have a significant effect on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

This result is connected with the study of Okoli et al., (2024) and Eboigbe et al., (2023), who looked at Machine learning in cybersecurity: A review of threat detection and defense mechanisms. The findings demonstrate a strong beneficial relationship between machine learning algorithms in cyber security. Machine learning algorithms thus tend to improve strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

4.1.3 HYPOTHESIS THREE (HO3)

Data collection and processing do not have a significant effect on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

Table 4.5 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.638 ^a	.407	.397	2.51449

a. Predictors: (Constant), Data collection and processing

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 4.6 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	281.504	1	281.504	44.523	.000 ^b
	Residual	410.973	65	6.323		
	Total	692.478	66			

a. Dependent Variable: Strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management

b. Predictors: (Constant), Data collection and processing

Source: Field Survey (2024)

The result above shows the model summary table that revealed the extent to which the variance in artificial intelligence can be explained by data collection and processing is 40.7% i.e. (R square = 0.407). The ANOVA table shows the Fcal 44.523. The significance level is .000 which implies a statistical confidence at 95%. Considering this, the decision would be to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) and accept the alternate hypothesis (Ho). This implies that the data collection and processing have a significant effect on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

This result aligns with the findings of Odonkor et al., 2024 and Kaggwa et al., 2024. In their studies on the use of AI in Decision Making: Transforming Business Strategies, in which the use of data collection and processing has a significant effect on decision-making. Data collection and processing thus tends to improve strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The application of artificial intelligence has a significant effect on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management. However, the specific conclusions on the objectives are; that cloud computing, machine learning algorithms, and data collection and processing have significant effects on strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management.

5.1 RECOMMENDATIONS

From the conclusion of the research, the following are the recommendations below.

- i. To achieve strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management, engineers should embrace cloud computing, which enables integration in construction management, offering scalability and flexibility, to also allow seamless scaling of computational resources based on project requirements, handle large data sets.
- ii. To achieve strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management, engineers should embrace the use of machine learning algorithms, this will improve the analysis of historical data for labor allocation, ensure proper equipment usage, help in material distribution, and enhance productivity and also identify potential risk factors to efficiently execute the construction of projects.
- iii. To ensure strategic decision-making in infrastructure engineering project management, data should be collected and processed through the use of artificial intelligence.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge Julius Berger Nigeria Plc for their invaluable support and the provision of data used in this study. Their contribution was critical to the successful completion of this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abioye, S. O., Oyedele, L. O., Akanbi, L., Ajayi, A., Delgado, J. M. D., Bilal, M., ... & Ahmed, A. (2021). Artificial intelligence in the construction industry: A review of present status, opportunities and future challenges. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 44(3), 272-299.
- [2] Abrahams T.O., Farayola, O.A., Kaggwa, S., Uwaoma, P.U., Hassan, A.O, & Dawodu, S.O. (2024). Reviewing Third-Party Risk Management: Best Practices in Accounting and Cybersecurity for Superannuation Organizations. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, 6(1), 21-39.

- [3] Adelekan, O. A., Adisa, O., Ilugbusi, B.S., Obi, O.C., Awonuga, K.F., Asuzu, O.F, et al. (2024). Evolving Tax Compliance in the Digital Era: A Comparative Analysis of AI-Driven Models and Blockchain Technology in US Tax Administration. *Computer Science & IT Research Journal*, 5(2), 311-335.
- [4] Adewusi, A.O., Asuzu, O.F, Olorunsogo, T., Iwuanyanwu, C., Adaga, E., Daraojimba, D.O. (2024). AI in precision agriculture: A review of technologies for sustainable farming practices. 2024.
- [5] Akour, I., Alnazzawi, N., Alshurideh, M., Almaiah, M.A., Al Kurdi, B., Alfaisal, R.M., Salloum, S., (2022). A Conceptual Model for Investigating the Effect of Privacy Concerns on E-Commerce Adoption: A Study on United Arab Emirates Consumers. *Electron*. 11, 36-48.
- [6] Al-Dmour, N.A., Ali, L., Salahat, M., Alshurideh, M., Alzoubi, H.M., Ghazal, T.M., Chabani, Z. (2023). Information Systems Solutions for the Database Problems. *Stud. Comput. Intell*. 12(1), 703–715.
- [7] Aljumah, A.I., Nuseir, M.T., Alam, M.M., (2021b). Traditional marketing analytics, big data analytics and big data system quality and the success of new product development. *Bus. Process Manag*, 27 (2), 1108–1125.
- [8] Aljumah, Ahmad Ibrahim, Nuseir, M.T., El Refae, G.A., (2022a). The effect of sensory marketing factors on customer loyalty during Covid 19: Exploring the mediating role of customer satisfaction. *Int. J. Data Netw. Sci*, 6(1), 1359–1368.
- [9] Al-Marouf, R.S., Alnazzawi, N., Akour, I., Ayoubi, K., Alhumaid, K., Nasser, N.M., Alaraimi, S., Al-Bulushi, A.A., Thabit, S., Alfaisal, R., Aburayya, A., Salloum, S., (2022b). Students' perception towards using electronic feedback after the pandemic: Post-acceptance study. *Int. J. Data Netw. Sci*, 6(1), 1233–1248.
- [10] Amiri, N. Al, Rahim, R.E.A., Ahmed, G., (2020). Leadership styles and organizational knowledge management activities: A systematic review. *Gadjah Mada Int. J. Bus*, 22, 250–275.
- [11] Atadoga, A., Osasona, F., Amoo, O.O, Farayola, O.A, Ayinla, B.S, Abrahams, T.O. (2024). The Role of it in Enhancing Supply Chain Resilience: A Global Review. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 6(2), 336-351.
- [12] Darko, A., Chan, A. P., Adabre, M. A., Edwards, D. J., Hosseini, M. R., & Ameyaw, E. E. (2020). Artificial intelligence in the AEC industry: Scientometric analysis and visualization of research activities. *Automation in construction*, 11(2), 103-118.
- [13] Eboigbe, E.O., Farayola, O.A., Olatoye, F.O., Nnabugwu, O.C., Daraojimba, C. (2023). Business intelligence Engineering Science & Technology Journal. 4(5), 285-307.
- [14] Kaggwa, S, Eleogu, T.F, Okonkwo, F, Farayola, O.A, Uwaoma, P.U, Akinoso, A. (2024). AI in Decision Making: Transforming Business Strategies. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*. 10(12), 423-444.
- [15] Mahmood, A., Al Marzooqi, A., El khatib, M. & AlAmeemi, H. (2023). How Artificial Intelligence can Leverage Project Management Information System (PMIS) and Data Driven Decision Making in Project Management. *International Journal of Business Analytics and Security (IJBAS)*, 3(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.54489/ijbas.v3i1.215>
- [16] Odonkor, B., Kaggwa, S., Uwaoma, P.U., Hassan, A. O., Farayola, O. A. (2024). Integrating Artificial Intelligence in Accounting: A Quantitative Economic Perspective for the Future of US Financial Markets. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, 6(1), 56-78.
- [17] Oguejiofor, B.B., Uzougbo, N. S, Kolade, A. O., Raji, A., Daraojimba, C. (2023). Review of Successful Global Public-Private Partnerships: Extracting key Strategies for Effective US Financial Collaborations. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 10(8), 312-331.
- [18] Okoli, U.I, Obi, O.C, Adewusi, A.O., Abrahams, T.O., (2024). Machine learning in cybersecurity: A review of threat detection and defense mechanisms, .
- [19] Rane, N., Lopes, S., Raval, A., Ruma, D., & Thakur, M. P. (2017). Study of effects of labour productivity on construction projects. *International Journal of Engineering Sciences and Research Technology*, 6(6), 15-20.
- [20] Reis, O., Eneh, N.E., Ehimuan, B., Anyanwu, A., Olorunsogo, T., Abrahams, T.O. (2024). Privacy Law Challenges in The Digital Age: A Global Review of Legislation and Enforcement. *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*, 6(1), 73-88.
- [21] Rogers E. M. (1962). *The diffusion of innovations*. Glencoe, IL: Free Press.
- [22] Sacks, R., Girolami, M., & Brilakis, I. (2020). Building information modelling, artificial intelligence and construction tech. *Developments in the Built Environment*, 4(1), 100-110.
- [23] Thakur, N., Nagrath, P., Jain, R., Saini, D., Sharma, N., Hemanth, D.J. (2021). Artificial intelligence techniques in smart cities surveillance using UAVs: A survey. *Machine Intelligence and Data Analytics for Sustainable Future Smart Cities*, 4(1), 329-353.
- [24] Valentina, E. A, Chinyere, E. E, Azuji, I. M. (2021). Emotional Intelligence as Correlate of Marital Satisfaction of Married Teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. *World Journal of Innovative Research*, 10(4), 122-127.
- [25] Viswanath Venkatesh, Fred D. Davis, (2000) A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. *Management Science* 46(2),186-204. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.46.2.186.11926>
- [26] Weng, W.H., Sellergen, A., Kiraly, A.P., D'Amour, A., Park, J., Pilgrim, R., Pfohl, S., Lau, C., Natarajan, V., Azizi, S., & Karthikesalingam, A. (2024). An intentional approach to managing bias in general purpose embedding models. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 6(2), e126-e130.
- [27] Yasir, A., Ahmad, A., Abbas, S., Inairat, M., Al-Kassem, A.H., Rasool, A., (2022). How Artificial Intelligence Is Promoting Financial Inclusion? A Study on Barriers of Financial Inclusion, in: 2022 International Conference on Business Analytics for Technology and Security (ICBATS). 1–6.
- [28] Zhou, W., Yan, Z., & Zhang, L. (2024). A comparative study of 11 non-linear regression models highlighting autoencoder, DNN, and SVR, enhanced by SHAP importance analysis in soybean branching prediction. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 59-70.